

1 **Modelling of calcium, phosphorus, and zinc fluxes in the gastrointestinal tract**
2 **of growing pigs**

3 J. Labarre ^{a,b}, C. Loncke ^b, A. Narcy ^c, M.Jlali ^d, P. Schlegel ^e, P.Schmidely ^b, M.P.
4 Létourneau-Montminy ^a

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6 ^a *Département des sciences animales, Université Laval, Québec, QC G1V 0A6,*
7 *Canada*

8 ^b *UMR Modélisation Systémique appliqué aux Ruminants, INRAe, AgroParisTech,*
9 *Université Paris-Saclay, 91120, Palaiseau, France*

10 ^c *UMR Biologie des Oiseaux et Aviculture, INRAe, Université de Tours, 37380,*
11 *Nouzilly, France.*

12 ^d *European Laboratory of Innovation, Science and Expertise, Adisseo France S.A.S,*
13 *69190, Saint-Fons, France*

14 ^e *Swine Research Group, Agroscope, 1725 Posieux, Switzerland.*

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16 Corresponding author: Marie-Pierre Létourneau-Montminy. Email : marie-
17 pierre.letourneau-montminy.1@ulaval.ca

18 **Abstract**

19 Improving phosphorus (P) utilization is a key strategy to enhance the sustainability of
20 pig production. Microbial phytase is widely used in pig nutrition to improve phytate P
21 (PP) degradation and P availability, but its efficacy is strongly influenced by the
22 digestive processes governing mineral solubilization along the gastrointestinal tract.
23 To map the determinants of phytase efficacy, a mechanistic model describing the
24 digestive fate of Ca, P, PP and zinc (Zn) in growing pigs was developed. The model

25 represents the stomach as a single, well-mixed compartment and the small intestine
26 as 180 sequential segments to capture spatial gradients in digestion and absorption.
27 Dietary and endogenous pools of Ca, P, PP and Zn were represented in soluble and
28 insoluble forms. Gastric phytate solubilization was modelled as a pH-dependent
29 process, phytate hydrolysis by microbial phytase followed Michaelis–Menten kinetics,
30 and intestinal mineral absorption as combined saturable and passive processes. The
31 model was implemented in Python and run over 1440 min. Five dietary scenarios were
32 simulated based on experimental diets: two Ca levels (low Ca, LCa; control Ca, CCa),
33 two phytase levels (0 or 500 FTU/kg), and one additional CCa diet with 2 000 FTU/kg
34 phytase. The model predicted a phytase dose-response for PP digestibility, increasing
35 from 22.5% without phytase to 80.7–81.1% with 500 FTU/kg and 88.8% with 2 000
36 FTU/kg. Simulated total tract digestibility of P increased from 50.2–55.3% to 69.2–
37 68.0% with 500 FTU/kg, Ca digestibility from 61.7–64.4% to 67.2–69.6%, and Zn
38 digestibility from 47.3–50.0% to 77.0–77.8%. 500 FTU/kg of phytase released
39 approximately 1.1 g/kg digestible P, close to the provided equivalency of 1.2 g/kg by
40 the supplier, whereas digestible Ca release was lower under LCa conditions (0.6 vs
41 1.2 g/kg expected). Sensitivity analysis indicated that PP digestibility was mainly driven
42 by phytase kinetics and gastric liquid retention time, whereas Ca digestibility was
43 primarily influenced by Ca absorption parameters. Model evaluation showed good
44 predictive performance for P ($n = 230$; $R^2 = 0.91$; RMPSE = 8.9%) and PP ($n = 29$; R^2
45 = 0.97; RMPSE = 11.7%), moderate performance for Ca ($n = 156$; $R^2 = 0.48$; RMPSE
46 = 12.4%), and poor performance for Zn ($n = 119$; $R^2 = 0.43$; RMPSE = 76.9%). Overall,
47 the model captured the main mechanisms governing P and Ca digestion and
48 highlighted the key roles of gastric pH, phytate hydrolysis, and intestinal complex
49 formation in determining mineral availability in pigs.

50 **Keywords:** Phytase, Digestion, Mechanistic Model, *In silico*, Minerals

51 **Implications**

52 Phosphorus and zinc are essential nutrients for farmed animals, and reducing their
53 excretion is important due to limited resources and environmental concerns. A
54 mechanistic model was built to map the fate of calcium, phosphorus, and zinc during
55 digestion in pigs and improve understanding of their utilisation. The model highlights
56 the importance of pH dynamics, buffering effects, and mineral interactions along the
57 digestive tract.

58 **Introduction**

59 Improving phosphorus (P) utilization is a key strategy to enhance the sustainability of
60 pig production systems. A better understanding of its digestive fate after ingestion is
61 beneficial to achieve this objective. In plant-based feed ingredients used in pig
62 nutrition, P is predominantly bound to inositol hexakisphosphate, also known as
63 phytate (Sauvant et al., 2004). However, pigs hydrolyse only a fraction of phytate,
64 resulting in an average digestibility of approximately 20% of phytate P (PP;
65 Létourneau-Montminy et al., 2012). Beyond its role as a P reservoir, phytate is also a
66 major antinutritional factor, capable of reducing the digestibility of cations such as
67 calcium (Ca) and zinc (Zn). Indeed, phytic acid is bound to cations (phytate) as an
68 insoluble complex, thereby limiting the absorption of these cations (Schlegel et al.,
69 2010; Bournazel et al., 2018).

70 Phytase is an enzyme capable of degrading PP, thereby increasing not only P
71 digestibility but also that of Ca and Zn by preventing the formation of insoluble phytate–
72 mineral complexes. To maintain the balance between absorbed Ca and P, it is

73 important to quantify the amount of Ca that can be “released” through phytase activity.
74 This amount depends on the number of Ca molecules bound per phytate molecule and
75 on phytase efficacy. Moreover, Ca carbonate (CaCO_3), the main dietary Ca source,
76 has a high buffering capacity (Lawlor et al., 2005), which may reduce phytase efficacy
77 by altering gastrointestinal pH conditions. The small intestine represents the primary
78 site for regulation of Zn metabolism through endogenous secretions and reabsorption
79 (Brugger, 2018). The presence of Zn from both endogenous and dietary origins
80 complicates the quantification of phytase effects on Zn digestibility. It has been
81 modelled that when dietary Zn is high ($>1,000$ mg/kg), the digestibility of P is reduced,
82 due to its binding with phytate (Labarre et al., 2025). Antagonistic effects of Zn on PP
83 degradation require further clarification. A better understanding of the mechanisms
84 underlying Ca- and Zn-mediated modulation of phytate degradation in the
85 gastrointestinal tract is an important step toward maximizing phytase efficacy. A
86 mechanistic representation of Ca, P, and Zn fluxes along the intestine would also
87 improve the understanding of factors influencing their bioavailability and the extent to
88 which phytase modulates these processes. Modelling provides a framework to
89 integrate existing knowledge and test hypotheses regarding the functioning of
90 biological systems (Sauvant, 1992). A mechanistic model describing the digestive fate
91 of P and Ca in pigs was first developed by Létourneau-Montminy et al. (2011).
92 However, this modelling framework does not, or only to a limited extent, explicitly
93 represent key processes such as the buffering effect of the diet, gastric pH dynamics,
94 the effects of new-generation of phytases, the *de novo* formation of mineral–phytate
95 and mineral–phosphate complexes (Ca–PP, Ca–P, Zn–PP) in the small intestine, and
96 the integration of Zn fluxes within the digestive tract.

97 The objective of the present study was to update this previous model by incorporating
98 a mechanistic representation of gastrointestinal pH kinetics and the buffering effects
99 of diets. The integration of Zn fluxes within the digestive tract, as well as the effects of
100 new generation phytases, was also included as a major objective of this modelling
101 approach.

102 **Material and methods**

103 ***Development***

104 *Model general structure.*

105 Model notations are reported in Table 1. The model simulates the process of dietary
106 (D) and endogenous (E) Ca, P, PP and Zn digestion in the gastro-intestinal tract (GIT)
107 of a growing pig of 50 kg BW (Figure 1). Only the stomach (S) and the small intestine
108 (SI) are represented in the model. The S is considered as a single compartment
109 immediately mixed and mineral pools are represented in soluble (s) and insoluble (i)
110 forms. It includes state variables representing dietary PP (SDPPI, SDPPs), dietary non
111 phytic phosphorus (NPP, SDNPPi, SDNPPs), dietary Ca (SDCai, SDCas, SDCaCO₃,
112 SDCav), dietary Zn (SDZni, SDZns), H⁺ (SH) and stomach fluid (SF). To represent the
113 interaction among Ca, P and Zn and the tubular structure of SI, the SI is represented
114 as a series of repeated structural units referred to as segments. These segments do
115 not represent distinct physiological compartments, but rather mathematical units used
116 to approximate spatial gradients along the intestinal tract. Although each segment
117 follows the same mathematical representation, it operates under segment-specific
118 conditions, (i.e., Ca, P, PP and Zn pool sizes), similarly to previous models (Rivest et
119 al., 2000; Garçon et al., 2025).

120 Each segment consists of 14 state variables representing mineral pools in soluble and
121 insoluble forms. Dietary PP is represented as intestinal dietary PP insoluble (IDPPi)
122 and soluble (IDPPs). Non phytic phosphorus pools, from dietary (IDNPPi, IDNPPs) and
123 endogenous (E) origin (IEPi, and IEPs) are also represented. Calcium from dietary and
124 endogenous origin is represented as IDCai, IDCas, IECai, and IECas. Zinc from dietary
125 and endogenous origin is represented as IDZni, IDZns, IEZni, and IEZns. State
126 variables are expressed on a DM basis (g), except H⁺ and fluid, which are expressed
127 in mmol and L respectively. Apparent ileal digestibility (AID) was calculated as the
128 difference between dietary input and dietary and endogenous output from the last
129 segment, divided by the dietary input. As large intestine is known to have limited effect
130 of the overall absorption of Ca, P and Zn (Liu et al., 2000; Ketata et al., 2024), AID
131 value was equal to apparent total tract digestibility (ATTD). The model was built in
132 Python version 3.11.10. The system of ordinary equations was solved using the
133 Range-Kutta 4th order method (Scipy package, version 1.15.0). The model was run for
134 1440min with a step time of 1 min. Parameter values were obtained from the literature
135 or physiological knowledge when feasible and the remaining parameters were
136 estimated from published data. Model parameter values are reported in Table 2, and
137 full model notations and equations are provided in Table 3. In the main text,
138 mechanisms are described using a “source → destination” notation (e.g., EXT →
139 SDNPPs), allowing readers to directly identify the corresponding equations in the
140 tables, where fluxes are consistently denoted using the same convention (e.g., EXT →
141 SDNPPs).

142 *Feed and nutrient intake.*

143 Feed intake is represented as a series of discrete meals occurring between defined
144 times (t_{first_meal}) and (t_{last_meal}). Daily DM intake is divided by the number of

145 meals per day (n_{meals}) to determine meal size. Each meal is consumed over a fixed
146 duration (meal_duration). The ingestion rate is determined by daily DM intake, n_{meals}
147 and meal_duration and is applied only within the defined feeding window (Strathe et
148 al., 2008; Schop et al., 2023). Feed intake drives the input of nutrients to the stomach
149 pools, calculated by multiplying the rate of feed intake with the concentration of the
150 respective nutrients in the diet. (e.g., $\text{EXT} \rightarrow \text{SDX}$, such as $\text{EXT} \rightarrow \text{SDNPPs}$; all dietary
151 input fluxes are defined using this convention, see Table 3). Dietary PP enters in the
152 SDPPi pool ($\text{EXT} \rightarrow \text{SDPPi}$). Non phytic phosphorus from plant or mineral sources is
153 partitioned between SDNPPs ($\text{EXT} \rightarrow \text{SDNPPs}$) and SDNPPi ($\text{EXT} \rightarrow \text{SDNPPi}$) as
154 proposed by Letourneau-Montminy et al. (2011). Briefly, each mineral source (i.e,
155 monocalcium phosphate, dicalcium phosphate, monosodium phosphate, plant and
156 animal NPP) have different solubility coefficients (solnppsx) derived from their
157 apparent digestibility value with monosodium phosphate as reference source (Sauvant
158 et al., 2004). Non phytic phosphorus is considered immediately solubilized; therefore,
159 the soluble amount of NPP enters in SDNPPs pool ($\text{EXT} \rightarrow \text{SDNPPs}$), while the
160 remaining NPP enters in the SDNPPi pool ($\text{EXT} \rightarrow \text{SDNPPi}$). Dietary CaCO_3 enters
161 the SDCaCO_3 pool ($\text{EXT} \rightarrow \text{SDCaCO}_3$). Dietary Ca ($\text{EXT} \rightarrow \text{SDCas}$) and Zn
162 ($\text{EXT} \rightarrow \text{SDZns}$) from mineral and animal sources enter the SCas and the SDZns pools,
163 respectively. Due to limited available data, no source-specific solubility coefficient was
164 applied for Ca and Zn. Dietary plant calcium (Cav ; $\text{EXT} \rightarrow \text{SDCap}$) and Zn (Znv ;
165 $\text{EXT} \rightarrow \text{SDZnv}$) are directed to insoluble pools due to complexation with PP.

166 *Stomach.*

167 Digesta passage rate through the stomach ($\text{SDX} \rightarrow \text{IDX}$, such as $\text{SDNPPs} \rightarrow \text{IDNPPs}$)
168 differs between the solid and liquid of digesta (Wilfart et al., 2007; Schop et al., 2019
169 and 2020). It was assumed that liquid digesta fraction contained soluble nutrient

170 (SDPPs, SDNPPs, SDCas, SDZns), whereas the solid digesta fraction contained
171 insoluble nutrients (SDPPI, SDNPPi, SDCai, SDZni). For each fraction, digesta
172 passage was modelled using first-order mass-action law and estimated as the inverse
173 of the mean retention time of liquid and solid phase (Bastianelli et al., 1996). The mean
174 retention times in the stomach were assumed to be 163 and 95 minutes for the solid
175 and liquid phases, respectively (Wilfart et al., 2007; Schop et al., 2019 and 2020).

176 Gastric fluid secretion was represented as a function of stomach content volume
177 (EXT→SDF). The secretion rate was assumed to increase proportionally with the total
178 gastric mass relative to a maximal stomach capacity (Malagelada et al., 1979). The
179 maximal stomach capacity was defined according to NRC (2012). The parameter k_{gs}
180 represents the maximal secretion rate and was derived from Zebrowska et al. (1983).

181 The concentration of H^+ in the gastric fluid (H_{gs}) was regulated as a function of luminal
182 pH (Moeller et al., 1974; Cranwell et al., 1976; Parsons, 1996) and was described by
183 a basal component (H_{gs0}) and a variable component (H_{gsv}), such that $H_{gs} = H_{gs0} +$
184 H_{gsv} (EXTe→SDH). As luminal pH approached acidic conditions (pH 2), the variable
185 component decreased, and total acid concentration converged toward the basal level
186 (H_{gs0} ; Parsons, 1996).

187 Two different representations of buffering capacity were implemented, depending on
188 whether buffering was assumed to arise from the entire meal or solely from $CaCO_3$. In
189 both cases, dissolution of the buffering component (meal or $CaCO_3$) was represented
190 as a first-order process governed by a dissolution rate constant (k_d), proportional to
191 both the amount of substrate present and the H^+ concentration. The buffering effect
192 was assumed to be proportional to the dissolution rate, thereby reducing the free H^+
193 pool (SDH → Buffer). The buffering capacity of the diet (k_{bbmeal}) or $CaCO_3$

194 (k_{bbCaCO_3}) was derived from acid-binding capacity measurements reported by
195 Lawlor et al. (2005).

196 The quantities of SDPPs insolubilization and SDPPi solubilization were represented as
197 a first-order process between insoluble and soluble pools. The forward rate constant
198 (k_{pp_sol}) was fixed at 0.05 (SDPPi \rightarrow SDPPs). The backward rate (SDPPs \rightarrow SDPPi)
199 constant (k_{pp_insol}) was defined as a function of the pH-dependent insoluble fraction
200 to ensure that the system converged toward a predefined equilibrium distribution. The
201 insoluble fraction was described using a logistic function of pH, bounded by the
202 minimum insolubility at low pH ($solpp_0$) and the maximum insolubility at high pH
203 ($solpp_inf$). The logistic parameter was derived from the specified pH inflection point
204 (pH_inf), ensuring a sigmoidal transition of phytate insolubility across the physiological
205 pH range (Grynspar and Cheryan, 1983). This formulation allowed the equilibrium
206 between soluble and insoluble phytate to dynamically adjust to luminal pH conditions.

207 Soluble PP degradation (SDPPs \rightarrow SDNPPs) was represented using a Michaelis–
208 Menten equation characterized by a maximum flux (V_{max_phytm} , V_{max_phytp}) and
209 an affinity constant (K_m_phytm , K_m_phytp). The parameters V_{max} and K_m were
210 estimated from *in vitro* data (Menezes-Blackburn et al., 2015). Enzyme efficacy was
211 defined as a function of pH, with both plant phytase ($Reff_phytp$) and microbial phytase
212 ($Reff_phytm$) assumed to be pH dependent. The model allows the simulation of
213 different microbial phytases (PhytM), each defined by specific kinetic parameters and
214 pH-dependent activity profiles. For plant phytase, an efficacy coefficient was applied
215 to the V_{max} component to account for the relative enzymatic activity due to protease
216 activity, as described by Letourneau-Montminy et al. (2011). Hydrolysis of PP by plant
217 and microbial phytases was assumed to be additive in the model (Zimmermann et al.,
218 2003).

219 *Small intestine.*

220 Limited differences between the retention times of solids and liquids digesta are
221 reported in SI (Wilfart et al., 2007; Schop et al., 2019 and 2020), consequently no
222 difference in digesta passes was considered in the SI. Transit in the SI was modelled
223 following the approach described by Garcon et al. (2025) using 180 sequential
224 segments corresponding to a total retention time of 180 min. Passage through each
225 segment was described using first-order kinetics, with the fractional passage rate
226 derived from the mean retention time and the number of segments ($IDX_i \rightarrow IDX_{i+1}$).
227 In the model, it was considered that PP enters the SI as IDPPs following gastric
228 emptying. The hydrolysis of PPs to NPPs in SI by endogenous enzymes ($IDPPs \rightarrow$
229 $IDNPPs$) was set at a constant fractional rate (k_{pp_hsi}) to obtain 22.5 % hydrolysis,
230 considering that 28% of IP6 are hydrolysed in the SI (Rodehutschord et al., 2022) and
231 IP6 represent 85% of PP in the SI without exogenous phytase (Schlemmer et al.,
232 2001). Insolubilization of PP in the SI ($IDPPs \rightarrow IDPPI$) was described by a fractional
233 rate ($k_{pp_insolsi}$), which was set to have most of PP insolubilized before half of small
234 intestine (Schlemmer et al., 2001). The insolubilisation of PPs is the driving force of
235 formation of Ca-PP complexes and Zn-PP complexes. One mol of PP binds up 3 mol
236 of Ca ($ncapp$; $IDCas \rightarrow IDCai$), as proposed by Letourneau-Montminy et al. (2011) and
237 up 0.12 mol of Zn ($nznpp$; $IDZns \rightarrow IDZni$; Labarre et al., 2025). The formation of
238 insoluble Ca-P complexes ($IDCas_j \rightarrow IDCai_j$ and $IDNPPs_j \rightarrow IDNPPi_j$) was also
239 represented based on the molar ratio between soluble inorganic phosphate and
240 soluble calcium. As proposed by Letourneau-Montminy et al. (2011), one mol of Cas
241 can bind up 1.5 mol of NPPs ($ncap$). Complex formations were allowed only when
242 molar ratio between Cas and NPPs was higher than 1.5. Precipitation proceeded
243 proportionally to total soluble Ca through a formation rate constant (kf_cap). In

244 addition, a maximum of 10% of soluble Ca was allowed to form insoluble complexes
245 over the entire small intestinal transit, corresponding to 10%/180 per segment, as
246 proposed by Letourneau-Montminy et al. (2011). Absorption of luminal soluble Ca, P,
247 and Zn from the intestinal lumen to the intestinal tissue (e.g., IDCas → blood, IDNPPs
248 → blood, IDZns → blood) was assumed to occur via both saturable transporters and
249 passive mechanisms. Saturable absorption was described using a Michaelis–Menten
250 equation characterized by a maximum flux (V_{max}) and an affinity constant (K_m) for
251 each mineral. Passive absorption was represented as a first-order process proportional
252 to the soluble luminal pool (e.g., $k_{aca} \times IDCas$ for Ca).

253 Endogenous secretions were represented as proposed by Rivest et al. (2000).
254 Pancreatic and biliary secretion were modulated by the meal passage in the first
255 segment of the SI. Endogenous is assumed to be affected positively by the gastric
256 emptying and negatively by the endogenous secretion itself. Endogenous P and Ca
257 secretions entered in the IENPPs and IECas pools, respectively. These secretions
258 were assumed to be theoretically 100% absorbable and to follow the same fate as
259 dietary fractions, including the formation of Ca–NPP complexes. Endogenous Ca was
260 also allowed to form complexes with PP, leading to its insolubilization. Basal
261 endogenous P and Ca secretions were set at 190 and 512 mg/kg feed, respectively,
262 based on NRC (2012) and Nelson et al. (2022). Their digestible proportions were
263 assumed to be 70% for endogenous P Gueguen and Perez (1981) and 55% for
264 endogenous Ca (Létourneau-Montminy et al., 2011).

265 Endogenous Zn secretions were represented in greater detail due to their major role
266 in metabolic regulation (Weigand and Kirchgessner, 1980). Pancreatic secretions were
267 assumed to range from 2.5 to 4.0 mg/d in a 50-kg pig receiving 60–180 mg Zn/d,
268 corresponding to approximately 3% of Zn intake. Biliary secretions were estimated at

269 0.9 mg/d based on an average Zn concentration of 0.35 mg/l and a bile secretion rate
270 of 2.6 l/d (Sullivan et al., 1981; Symonds and Charmley, 1990; Hedemann et al., 1998).
271 Desquamation of intestinal epithelial cells was also considered a source of
272 endogenous Zn. Assuming that a 50-kg pig contains approximately 250 g of protein in
273 the intestinal wall (Garçon et al., 2025), with an average Zn concentration of 80 mg/kg
274 of protein (Bueno Dalto et al., 2023) and applying a daily turnover rate of 20% of the
275 intestinal wall, this corresponds to an endogenous Zn loss of approximately 4 mg/d.

276 ***Simulation scenario***

277 To test how the model responds to contrasting Ca–P supply and phytase inputs, we
278 defined five dietary scenarios built from the experimental diets. Diets were formulated
279 to meet or exceed requirements for a 40 kg pigs. Two basal Ca levels were created: a
280 control Ca diet (CCa) and a low Ca diet (LCa). Within each Ca level, microbial phytase
281 (PhytM) was added at 0 or 500 FTU/kg (CCa-PhytM0, CCa-PhytM500; LCa-PhytM0,
282 LCa-PhytM500). An equivalency of +1.2 g STTD P and +1.2 g Ca per 500 FTU was
283 applied by proportionally reducing limestone and monocalcium phosphate. Finally, a
284 high-phytase “on-top” scenario (CCa-PhytM2000) consisted of CCa-PhytM500 with an
285 additional 1 500 FTU/kg was also simulated. Other simulation has been done to
286 illustrate the behaviour of the model (data not shown) and used in discussion.

287 ***Sensitivity analysis***

288 To identify the key drivers of model behaviour across dietary scenarios, a sensitivity
289 analysis was performed combining local univariate perturbation. First, an univariate
290 sensitivity analysis was conducted by varying each parameter individually around its
291 nominal value while keeping all others fixed. Parameters varied -50%, -25%, 25% and

292 50% of their initial value. This analysis was performed across the five dietary scenarios
293 defined above; however, for clarity, only the results of scenario CCa-PhytM500 are
294 presented here. As proposed by Schop et al. (2023), the sensitivity per in- and output
295 parameter (i) is expressed as:

$$296 \quad S_{y,x} = \frac{\frac{(y_{i\pm\Delta} - y_i)}{y_i}}{\frac{|x_{i\pm\Delta} - x_i|}{x_i}}$$

297 Where, y = the value of the selected model output parameter, and x = the value of the
298 driving variable or constant model parameter, i = the value according to the initial
299 settings without change, and $i \pm \Delta$ = the value according to the changed setting. The
300 results can be interpreted as follows: 1) a negative $S_{y,xi}$ indicates that the output
301 parameter decreases as a result of changing the input parameter, whereas a positive
302 $S_{y,xi}$ indicates that the output parameter increases as a result of changing the input
303 parameter, and 2) as $|S_{y,xi}|$ is a relative value it ranges from 0 to 1, whereby a value
304 of 0 indicates there is no response in the output parameter after changing the input
305 parameter, while a value of 1 indicates that the relative change in the output parameter
306 is equal to the relative change in the input parameter. Hence, the higher the absolute
307 value, the more sensitive the output parameter is to a change in the input parameter.

308 ***Model evaluation***

309 Model predictions of nutrient digestion kinetics were evaluated using independent in-
310 vivo data. Model evaluation comprised the predictions of the apparent total tract
311 digestibility (ATTD) of Ca, P and Zn. Data used for model evaluation were collected
312 from literatures: (1) Ca-P database reported 43 publications, 55 experiments and 230
313 treatments for ATTD of P and 28 publications, 36 experiments and 158 treatments for
314 ATTD of Ca; and (2) Zn database reported 16 publications, 18 experiments and 119

315 treatments for ATTD of Zn. For each simulation, dietary nutrient composition was
316 calculated using NRC (2012) tabulated ingredient values, including PP, NPP from
317 vegetal and mineral sources (NPPv, NPPa), mineral phosphates (MCP, DCP, MSP),
318 other mineral sources (othermin), vegetal and mineral calcium sources (Cav, Camin,
319 CaCO₃), zinc sources (Znv, Znmin, ZNa), and dietary buffering capacity (Lawlor et al.,
320 2005). Animals were assumed to receive six meals per day, and average daily feed
321 intake was set at 1.8 kg, corresponding to the mean intake of 50-kg pigs under
322 standard conditions. These inputs were used to drive dynamic simulations of digestive
323 and absorptive processes. Direct comparison between model predictions and
324 experimental observations was not considered appropriate due to the inter-
325 experimental heterogeneity (Sauvant et al., 2020). To account for this heterogeneity,
326 a statistical model including experiment as a fixed effect was applied Offner and
327 Sauvant (2004) :

$$328 \quad ATTD_{o_{ij}} = \mu + \mu_i + (\beta + \beta_i) \times ATTD_{p_{ij}} + \varepsilon_{ij}$$

329 where $ATTD_{o_{ij}}$ is the apparent digestibility coefficient observed in publication, $ATTD_{p_{ij}}$
330 is the one simulated for experiment i and treatment j , μ is the intercept, μ_i is the fixed
331 effect of the experiment on the intercept, β_i the experiment effect on the slope of the
332 regression, β the slope of the regression, and ε_{ij} the residual error. Evaluation of model
333 predictions were carried out based.

334 **Results**

335 ***General model behaviour***

336 Proton inflow originates from (1) meal, (2) gastric content from the fasted state and
337 predominantly (3) acid secretion during fed state (Figure 2). Protons outflows include
338 (1) buffering effect of the meal and (2) gastric emptying of acidic chyme into the SI

339 compartment. Gastric volume is dynamically modelled, varying over time with secretion
340 and emptying, thereby directly influencing luminal proton concentration and pH (Figure
341 3).

342 In PhytM0 diet, SDPPs and SDPPi phytate pools oscillated after each meal. Phytate
343 distribution between soluble and insoluble was primarily driven by luminal pH (Figure
344 4). Phytase supplementation introduced an irreversible degradation of soluble phytate,
345 shifting the equilibrium over time. Maximum hydrolysis occurred immediately after
346 feeding, acting on the soluble pool (SDPPs). As SDPPs were degraded, additional
347 phytate was solubilised from the insoluble pool to re-establish equilibrium, resulting in
348 progressive depletion of both pools. The magnitude of hydrolysis and the rate of
349 phytate hydrolysis increased with phytase dose (Figure 4, 5 and 6). Apparent
350 digestibility results are presented in Table 4.

351 ***Sensitivity analysis***

352 Sensitivity analysis indicated that model outputs were mainly influenced by parameters
353 related to phytate hydrolysis, passage kinetics, and mineral absorption (Table 5). The
354 AID of PP was most sensitive to changes in v_{max_phytm} (0.22 to 0.43% per 1%
355 change) and si_mrtl (0.25 to 0.50% per 1% change), followed by km_phytm , which
356 showed a negative effect (-0.23 to -0.32% per 1% change). Smaller effects were
357 observed for $Vs0$ (up to 0.16% per 1% change), kpp_sol (up to 0.08% per 1% change),
358 and kpp_hsi (0.08 to 0.10% per 1% change), whereas the other parameters had
359 negligible effects. The ATTD of Ca was primarily sensitive to v_{maxca} (0.41 to 0.87%
360 per 1% change), followed by $kmca$, which showed a negative effect (-0.28 to -0.34%
361 per 1% change). Passage parameters, including si_mrt and si_mrtl , also contributed
362 to ATTD Ca (up to 0.45 and 0.32% per 1% change, respectively), while other

363 parameters had minor effects. The ATTD of P was moderately sensitive to phytase-
364 related parameters, including v_{max_phytm} (0.14 to 0.28% per 1% change) and
365 km_phytm (-0.15 to -0.20% per 1% change), as well as to R_{canpp} (-0.14 to -0.17%
366 per 1% change). The ATTD of Zn was mainly affected by si_mrtl (0.32 to 0.55% per
367 1% change), v_{max_phytm} (0.26 to 0.43% per 1% change), km_phytm (-0.24 to
368 -0.39% per 1% change), $nznpp$ (-0.38 to -0.48% per 1% change), and v_{maxzn} (0.13
369 to 0.28% per 1% change).

370 ***Model evaluation***

371 The apparent digestibility of Ca, P, and PP was evaluated by comparing observed and
372 predicted values across datasets (Table 6 and Figure 7). For Ca, the model slightly
373 underestimated digestibility (61.6 ± 13.38 vs $58.1 \pm 13.49\%$), with moderate predictive
374 accuracy ($R^2 = 0.48$) and a relative mean prediction error (RMPSE) of 12.4%. The
375 prediction error was predominantly explained by random error (73.1%), with smaller
376 contributions from error due to central tendency (21.2%) and regression (5.7%). For P,
377 predicted values were in close agreement with observations (52.0 ± 17.13 vs $49.8 \pm$
378 16.54%), with high predictive accuracy ($R^2 = 0.91$) and a lower RMPSE (8.9%). The
379 prediction error was largely attributed to random error (75.4%), with negligible
380 contributions from central tendency (24.5%) and regression (0.1%). For PP, the model
381 tended to overestimate digestibility (57.9 ± 34.21 vs $62.7 \pm 32.51\%$), despite a high
382 coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.97$). The prediction error (RMPSE = 11.7%) was
383 mainly explained by random error (50.9%), with substantial contributions from central
384 tendency (47.7%) and minor regression error (1.4%). For Zn, the model overestimated
385 digestibility (27.7 ± 12.93 vs $41.0 \pm 11.58\%$), with a low coefficient of determination (R^2
386 = 0.43). The prediction error (RMPSE = 76.9%) was mainly explained by central

387 tendency (39.2%), with substantial contributions from disturbance (36.3%) and
388 regression error (24.5%).

389 **Discussion**

390 The objective of the model was to increase the understanding of phytate hydrolysis in
391 the digestive tract of pigs and its impact on the digestive fate of Ca, P and Zn, as well
392 as other modulating factors. Focus has been put on the mechanistic representation of
393 stomach pH variations, of digesta passage in SI and of *de novo* formation of Ca-PP,
394 Ca-P and Zn-PP complexes in the SI. While sharing similarities in overall structure with
395 the model of Létourneau-Montminy et al. (2011), the current model account for the
396 dietary buffering effects on gastric pH, the differential transit of liquid and solid phases
397 in the stomach and included a mechanistic representation of transit kinetics in the small
398 intestine. In addition, it incorporates a dynamic representation of phytate
399 insolubilization in the small intestine, as well as the *de novo* formation and dissociation
400 of Ca-PP, Ca-P, and Zn-PP complexes. The model also integrates dietary Zn fate
401 along the GIT following Ca and P approach.

402 **Gastric pH**

403 The model output of gastric pH showed three distinct phases following meal ingestion:
404 an initial increase, a moderate decrease and a pronounced decline. The initial increase
405 in pH is attributed to the buffering effect of the ingested feed and the dilution of basal
406 gastric juice present in the compartment, which depends on the interval since the
407 previous meal. Indeed, the decrease can be attributed to both the onset of gastric acid
408 secretion and the reduction in gastric volume as digesta is emptied into the SI. The
409 rate of pH decline is moderated by the buffering capacity of the ingested feed. Once

410 gastric emptying and acid secretion slow, the pH stabilizes. This pattern is consistent
411 with the qualitative trend reported by Blaabjerg et al. (2011), Bornhorst et al. (2013),
412 and Malagelada et al. (1979) in human who observed similar pH fluctuations in
413 response to meal ingestion in humans. Several mathematical models of gastric pH
414 were proposed. Letourneau-Montminy et al. (2011) used a modified Haldane function
415 to represent the function. This representation allowed an increase in pH after meal
416 ingestion followed by a pronounce decline. The concept used in the present model
417 shares similarity with the model of Rivera Del Rio et al. (2022) developed to represent
418 protein digestion in human. This model explicitly represents the parietal secretion H⁺
419 and the buffering effect of protein digestion. The parietal secretion of H⁺ differs with
420 the present model, Rivera Del Rio et al. (2022) choose a ON/OFF, i.e. parietal
421 secretion occurred when stomach volume is higher than basal volume of the stomach
422 when the parietal secretion in the present model linked the volume of the stomach to
423 parietal secretion. Rivera Del Rio et al. (2022) represents the buffering effect of protein
424 digestion as forward and backward reaction between protonated and de-protonated
425 protein states of protein. Weinstein et al. (2013) choose a similar representation for
426 buffering effect of the whole meal. In the present model, the system is described as a
427 unidirectional process rather than a full reversible equilibrium. An improvement to the
428 model would be to adopt the representation proposed by Weinstein et al. (2013).
429 However, dynamic data on gastric pH are needed to further refine and validate the
430 model.

431 ***Phytate hydrolysis***

432 *Stomach*

433 Sensitivity analysis identified that PP degradation was highly sensitive to parameters
434 governing phytate solubilisation and microbial phytase kinetics (v_{max_phytm} and
435 k_{m_phytm}), as well as gastric residence time of the liquid phase. In parallel, model
436 evaluation showed that PP digestibility was slightly overestimated, with a substantial
437 contribution of central tendency to the prediction error. Taken together, these results
438 suggest that the current representation of phytate solubility and/or phytase kinetics
439 may lead to an overestimation of phytate availability for hydrolysis, thereby explaining
440 the systematic bias observed for PP digestibility. The main assumption of the model is
441 that only soluble phytate can be degraded by phytase (O'Dell and De Boland, 1976).
442 The soluble PP has been modelled has forward and backward function to reach a
443 predefined equilibrium between soluble and insoluble phytate, as proposed by
444 Letourneau-Montminy et al. (2011). The predefined equilibrium is as function of gastric
445 pH. Thus, the representation of gastric pH considering the buffering capacity allowed
446 to simulate diets with different buffering capacity. As shown in Figure 4, the buffering
447 effect of the diet limits the solubilisation of phytate, i.e. more Ca from $CaCO_3$ increases
448 the buffering effect of diet reducing PP solubility. However, this effect is limited in
449 presence of PhytM. Indeed, PhytM hydrolysed soluble phytate and forced the
450 solubilisation to reach the predefined equilibrium. These results are in agreement with
451 in-vitro results who reported that more phytate is degraded than the amount that was
452 originally soluble (Pontoppidan et al., 2007a). As Pontoppidan et al. (2007a)
453 hypothesized phytate solubilise as a consequence of phytate degradation. Thus, can
454 explain the moderate negative effect of Ca on PhytM efficacy to hydrolyse phytate
455 and explained the limited effect of Ca on phytate hydrolysis observed in-vivo (Hu et al.,
456 2022; Klein et al., 2023; Klein et al., 2024).

457 Looking in details to the data, Hu et al. (2022) reported that IP6 degradation was 88%
458 with 1.2 g Ca/kg and 73 % for 5.8 or 9.6 g Ca/kg. In comparison, the model predicted
459 values of 80.2% and 79.4%, respectively. This can illustrate limitation in phytate
460 solubilisation and degradation representation. Distinct profiles of soluble phytate have
461 been observed in vitro between 1.2 and 6.2 g Ca/kg highlighting the strong interaction
462 between Ca and phytate solubility (Pontoppidan et al., 2007b). At pH 5, the model
463 predicted 35% of soluble phytate independently of Ca level. However, at the same pH,
464 with phytate from maize and soja, about 60% of phytate remained soluble in vitro with
465 1.2 g Ca/kg, whereas phytate solubility was close to zero at 6.2 and 11 g Ca/ kg
466 (Pontoppidan et al., 2007a). This suggests that, at low Ca concentration, PhytM can
467 act earlier because more phytate remains soluble, while at 6.2 and 11 g Ca/kg phytate
468 hydrolysis can only begin once pH decreases below approximately 4 where phytate
469 becomes sufficiently soluble (Pontoppidan et al., 2007a). Thus, in vitro experiment
470 where pH decreased gradually and the buffering effect of CaCO₃ were counteracted,
471 it takes 45 min to totally hydrolyse IP6 with 1.2 g Ca/kg, whereas 75 min are needed
472 with 6.2 and 11.2 g Ca/kg and 120 min with 21.2 g Ca/kg (Pontoppidan et al., 2007a).
473 It is well established that phytic acid forms insoluble complexes with divalent cations,
474 and that increasing the mineral:phytate molar ratio enhances the extent of complex
475 formation (Grynspan and Cheryan, 1983) and may change phytate solubility profile.
476 The impact of Ca on phytate solubility curve, independently of impact of CaCO₃ on pH
477 dynamics, was not taken in account in the present model. Incorporating a Ca-
478 dependent solubility function into the model could improve the understanding of
479 phytate degradation. The phytate solubility is represented as a sigmoidal relationship
480 between pH and soluble phytate. This function could be modulated by Ca
481 concentration. More data about the soluble phytate profile depending of pH, with Ca

482 concentration between 1.2 and 15 g Ca/kg will be necessary. High dietary Zn levels,
483 often supplied as ZnO, are known to reduce phytate degradation (Labarre et al., 2025),
484 partly due to their strong buffering capacity. This suggests that, as observed for Ca, Zn
485 may simultaneously affect gastrointestinal pH and phytate solubility. However, the
486 limited impact of Ca in the present model also indicates that phytase activity can
487 partially overcome reduced initial solubility by progressively releasing phytate from
488 insoluble complexes.

489 Another important point that the model was evaluated against digestibility. Digestibility
490 are aggregated measurement and misrepresentation discussion before were about the
491 dynamics of the system. To our knowledge, no dynamics data about phytate
492 solubilisation and degradation in pigs are reported in the literature and such data are
493 needed to better capture the effect Ca on phytate degradation. This limitation should
494 therefore be interpreted in relative terms. The good agreement between observed and
495 predicted values for PP and P digestibility indicates that, despite some limitations in
496 the representation of degradation mechanisms, the model adequately captures the
497 main underlying processes. Overall, the model reproduces the observed digestive
498 response with good accuracy, although simplified mechanistic descriptions may limit
499 its ability to fully account for Ca effects on phytate degradation.

500 *Small intestine.*

501 Phytate degradation by PhytM in the small intestine was not represented in the model.
502 The good agreement between observed and predicted AID PP supports this
503 assumption, suggesting that phytase activity in this segment is limited, as previously
504 reported by Kemme et al. (2005). In the SI, the model accounts for phytate hydrolysis
505 by endogenous phosphatase which was parametrized to reach 22.5% of phytate

506 hydrolysis at the end of the SI. Rodehutschord et al. (2022) showed that phytate
507 hydrolysis in SI varied from 10 to 40 % in the absence of phytase. A part of this variation
508 can be explained by the Ca concentration of diet, as Hu et al. (2022) reported that Ca
509 reduced the amount of phytate hydrolysis in the SI. As such increasing (1.2 vs 9.1 g
510 Ca/kg) dietary Ca content does not have an impact on the expression level of mucosal
511 phosphatases as showed by Hu et al. (2022). One explanation may be that high dietary
512 Ca inhibit phytate solubility and availability for hydrolysis. Currently, phytate
513 insolubilisation in segment n is described as a first-order process assuming a constant
514 rate coefficient. However, Ca is likely to modulate this process, implying that constant
515 rate coefficient may depend on Ca concentration.

516 ***De novo formation of complexes in the small intestine and impact of***
517 ***“liberated” amount calcium, phosphorus and zinc.***

518 *Digestible mineral equivalency of microbial phytase.*

519 Simulations from 0 to 4 000 FTU/kg indicate a curvilinear increase in digestible P,
520 digestible Ca and digestible Zn, with the response tending towards a plateau at high
521 phytase doses. According to the current model structure, predicted values increased
522 from 0 at 0 FTU/kg to 1.9 g/kg for digestible P, 1.2 g/kg for digestible Ca, 2.2 g/kg for
523 total Ca, and 48.0 mg/kg for digestible Zn at 4 000 FTU/kg. These values were similar
524 to those reported by Espinosa et al. (2022), who observed values up to 1.9 g/kg for
525 digestible P, 1.3 g/kg for digestible Ca and 2.2 g/kg for total Ca at 4 000 FTU/kg.
526 Phytate insolubilisation in the SI is a key driver of mineral availability in the model, as
527 it governs the *de novo* formation of Ca– and Zn–phytate complexes. This process is
528 described using fixed stoichiometric coefficients, with $n_{capp} = 3$ for Ca and $n_{znpp} =$
529 0.12 for Zn. Consequently, model predictions of mineral availability strongly depend on

530 these assumptions. Sensitivity analysis showed that kpp_insolsi negatively affected
531 Ca and Zn digestibility, especially when no PhytM is added (Data not shown). Phytate
532 hydrolysis reduces the availability of binding sites for Ca and Zn, preventing complex
533 formation and increasing the fraction of minerals remaining in a soluble and absorbable
534 form. The good agreement between observed and predicted values for P and Ca
535 digestibility suggests that the model adequately captures the effect of phytase on these
536 minerals, supporting the validity of the underlying assumptions, including the chosen
537 stoichiometric coefficients for Ca. In contrast, validation for Zn remains more uncertain,
538 likely due to the greater variability and limitations in available data, making it more
539 difficult to assess the accuracy of model predictions for this mineral.

540 *Impact of calcium on phytase on predicted equivalency of digestible phosphorus.*

541 The model highlights a strong influence of Ca on the predicted PhytM values for
542 digestible mineral equivalencies, likely driven by the formation of Ca–phosphate
543 complexes (Table 5). Simulations were conducted using a basal diet containing 2.6
544 g/kg PP, 1.3 g/kg NPPv, and 1.2 g/kg Ca, with additional Ca levels (0, 5, 10, and 20
545 g/kg) achieved through limestone supplementation. While phytase-mediated phytate
546 degradation remained relatively stable with 1.5 g PP / kg hydrolysed between 1.2 and
547 11.2 g Ca/kg and 1.3 with 20 g Ca/kg. The effect of Ca is more pronounced for
548 digestible P, which decreased markedly with increasing Ca, indicating that not all
549 liberated P is available for absorption, with values of 1.39, 1.47, 1.33, and 1.02 g/kg at
550 1.2, 6.2, 11.2, and 21.2 g/kg Ca, respectively. This discrepancy between P liberated
551 and P absorbed reflects the formation of insoluble Ca–P complexes and highlights that
552 phytate degradation does not directly translate into digestible P.

553 ***Endogenous secretion of zinc and zinc homeostasis.***

554 In contrast to P and Ca, model predictions for Zn digestibility showed low accuracy and
555 substantial bias. This may partly reflect the simplified representation of Zn dynamics,
556 where endogenous Zn secretions are assumed to be constant. A better description of
557 endogenous Zn flows may therefore be required to properly represent the digestive
558 fluxes of Zn. The simulation estimated endogenous Zn secretions in the intestine at
559 6.7 mg, which is of the same order of magnitude as values reported by Chu et al.
560 (2009) based on isotopic measurements. However Chu et al. (2009) shows that
561 endogenous Zn increases with addition of PhytM, limiting the apparent digestibility of
562 Zn. Weigand and Kirchgessner (1980) showed in rats, that increased true Zn
563 absorption increased endogenous secretion in the digestive tract. This constant
564 endogenous Zn secretion is therefore the major limitation in the present model. Within
565 this framework, endogenous secretions are not considered a direct reflection of the
566 physiological and nutritional status of the animal. Indeed, changes in pancreatic
567 secretions and Zn accumulation in the intestinal wall are processes that require several
568 weeks to be established (Windisch, 2003). Therefore, the time scale used in the
569 present model does not allow, as a first approximation, the integration of interactions
570 between digestion and metabolism. This raises the question of the relevance of linking
571 short-term digestion models with longer-term metabolic models, particularly to better
572 understand the digestive fate and homeostasis of Zn. Future developments of the
573 model could, however, improve the representation of Zn homeostatic mechanisms.

574 ***Absorption of calcium, phosphorus and zinc in the small intestine.***

575 Absorption processes in the small intestine play a central role in determining mineral
576 digestibility, although their relative importance differs between Ca, P and Zn. For Ca,
577 sensitivity analysis showed that absorption appeared to be a limiting step in the model.
578 As absorption approaches its maximum capacity, increases in luminal Ca availability

579 do not translate proportionally into increased uptake. Consequently, model predictions
580 become highly dependent on the parameterization of Ca absorption kinetics (v_{maxca}
581 and k_{mca}), highlighting both the importance and the difficulty of accurately estimating
582 these parameters. The model showed a good agreement between observed and
583 predicted Ca digestibility. However, the prediction error is largely dominated by
584 unexplained random variation (high ED), suggesting that important sources of
585 variability are still not captured by the model. The model struggles to accurately
586 reproduce Ca digestibility, particularly under conditions of high dietary P. For example,
587 in the study of Vipperman et al. (1974) who used a 3×3 factorial design (three Ca and
588 three P levels), Ca digestibility were consistent with observations at both low Ca–low
589 P (56 vs 58 %) and high Ca–high P (68 vs 66 %) levels. However, under low Ca and
590 high P conditions, the model fails to capture the observed response (66 vs 54 %). This
591 suggests that, in such situations, Ca absorption not driven solely by digestive
592 processes, but also by metabolic regulation. The digestibility of Ca is further
593 complicated by the strong homeostatic regulation of Ca absorption, which varies with
594 physiological status and dietary conditions (Oster et al., 2026) and thus can explain
595 the high ED of RMSE.

596 In contrast, P absorption appeared less limiting in the model. This may reflect the
597 relatively high availability of P once released from phytate, as well as the presence of
598 both passive and active absorption pathways. However, it may also indicate that P
599 absorption has been less constrained during model development, and further research
600 is needed to better characterize and calibrate intestinal Ca uptake. Zinc absorption
601 presents similar challenges to Ca, as it is also governed by saturable and highly
602 regulated transport mechanisms. Zinc homeostasis relies on a complex network of
603 transporters that adapt to dietary supply, making absorption efficiency variable and

604 difficult to represent using fixed parameters. In addition, strong interactions between
605 Zn and phytic acid complicate the distinction between luminal availability and
606 absorptive capacity. Future model developments should therefore aim to better
607 integrate adaptive mechanisms governing mineral absorption in order to improve the
608 representation of mineral homeostasis.

609 **Conclusion**

610 This study developed a dynamic mechanistic model describing the digestive fate of
611 Ca, P, PP, Zn and PhytM in growing pigs. The model captured the main processes
612 governing P and Ca digestion, including phytate hydrolysis, gastric pH dynamics, and
613 intestinal complex formation, and reproduced the strong dose-dependent response to
614 PhytM. Results highlighted that PP degradation does not directly translate into mineral
615 availability, as Ca–phosphate interactions can limit P absorption. Model evaluation
616 showed good predictive performance for P and PP, and moderate accuracy for Ca,
617 with prediction error largely driven by unexplained variability, suggesting that additional
618 regulatory mechanisms are not fully captured. Sensitivity analysis identified PhytM
619 kinetics, gastric retention time, and Ca absorption as key drivers of model behaviour.
620 Overall, the model provides a mechanistic framework to better understand Ca–P–
621 PhytM interactions in pig nutrition. Future developments should focus on improving the
622 representation of Ca-dependent PP solubility and integrating metabolic regulation of
623 Ca absorption to enhance predictive capacity.

624 **Ethics approval**

625 Not applicable

626 **Data and model availability statement**

627 Script of the model is available online via the following link:
628 https://github.com/jlabarre3/GIT_CaPZn_Phytate.git. Information can be made
629 available from the authors upon request.

630 **Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing** 631 **process**

632 During the preparation of this work, the authors used AI to check the grammar and
633 clarity of the text. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as
634 needed and took full responsibility for the content of the publication.

635 **Author ORCIDs**

636 J. LABARRE: <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-2883-0333>

637 C. LONCKE: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5551-8542>

638 A. NARCY: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8517-2172>

639 M. JLALI: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9741-3095>

640 P. SCHLEGEL: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5095-0889>

641 P. SCHMIDELY: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7566-7868>

642 M.P. LÉTOURNEAU-MONTMINY : <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5364-2662>

643 **Declaration of interest**

644 Maamer Jlali is an Adisseo employers. The other authors declare that they have no
645 known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have
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652 **Credit author contributions**

653 J. LABARRE: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Writing –
654 original draft.

655 C. LONCKE: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing.

656 A. NARCY: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing.

657 M. JLALI: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing.

658 P. SCHLEGEL: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing.

659 P. SCHMIDELY: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing.

660 M.P. LÉTOURNEAU-MONTMINY : Conceptualization, Methodology, Funding
661 acquisition, Project administration, Writing – review & editing.

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835
836

837 **Table 1**

838 Model notation and abbreviations

	Definition	units
State variable		
SDQs	Stomach Dietary Solid	g
SDQL	Stomach Dietary Liquid	g
SDNPPs	Stomach Dietary Non Phytic Phosphorus soluble	g
SDNPPi	Stomach Dietary Non Phytic Phosphorus insoluble	g
SDPPs	Stomach Dietary Phytic Phosphorus soluble	g
SDPPi	Stomach Dietary Phytic Phosphorus insoluble	g
SDCaCO3	Stomach Dietary Calcium Carbonate	gCa
SDCas	Stomach Dietary Calcium soluble	g
SDCai	Stomach Dietary Calcium insoluble	g
SDCav	Stomach Dietary Calcium vegetal	g
SDZns	Stomach Dietary Zinc soluble	g
SDZni	Stomach Dietary Zinc insoluble	g
SDZnv	Stomach Dietary Zinc vegetal	g
SDPHYTM	Stomach Dietary Phytase Microbial	FTU
SDPHYTV	Stomach Dietary Phytase Vegetal	FTU
SH	Stomach Proton	mmol
SEF	Stomach Endogenous Fluid	l
IDNPPs	Intestinal Dietary Non Phytic Phosphorus soluble	g
IDNPPi	Intestinal Dietary Non Phytic Phosphorus insoluble	g
IDPPs	Intestinal Dietary Phytic Phosphorus soluble	g
IDPPi	Intestinal Dietary Phytic Phosphorus insoluble	g
IDCas	Intestinal Dietary Calcium soluble	g
IDCai	Intestinal Dietary Calcium insoluble	g
IDZns	Intestinal Dietary Zinc soluble	g
IDZni	Intestinal Dietary Zinc insoluble	g
IEPs	Intestinal Endogenous Phosphorus soluble	g
IEPi	Intestinal Endogenous Phosphorus insoluble	g
IECas	Intestinal Endogenous Calcium soluble	g
IECai	Intestinal Endogenous Calcium insoluble	g
IEZns	Intestinal Endogenous Zinc soluble	g
IEZni	Intestinal Endogenous Zinc insoluble	g

839

840

841 **Table 2**

842 Parameter values of the model, with their name, corresponding description, unit and
 843 value. The model was parametrised to represent the small intestine of a growing pig
 844 of approximately 50 kg of BW.

Parameter	Description	Unit	value
Diet			
dmi	Dry matter intake	kg	
nmeals	Number of meals per day	/d	
meal_dur	Duration of meal intake	min	
meal_int	Meal interval	min	
feed_start	Clock-time of initial meal	min	
feed_end	Clock-time of final meal	min	
Passage			
s_mrts	Mean retention time of solid in the stomach	min	163
s_mrtl	Mean retention time of solid in the stomach	min	95
si_mrt	Mean retention time in the small intestine	min	180
nseg	Number of intestinal segments		180
Gastric secretions			
V _{s0}	Basal gastric volume	l	0.162
V _{smax}	Maximum gastric volume	l	2.0
kgs	Rate of gastric secretion	l/min	0.006
Hgs0	Basal proton concentration in gastric juice	mmol/l	20
HgsV	Variable proton concentration in gastric juice	mmol/l	60
kd	Dissociation constant	min ⁻¹	0.2
kbbm	Rate of buffering effect of meal	meq/g	
kbb _{CaCO₃}	Rate of buffering effect of calcium carbonate	meq/g	
Phytate solubilization			
pH_inf	pH at inflection point		5.63

solpp_0	Soluble phytate at pH equal to 0		0.88
solpp_inf	Soluble phytate at pH equal to infinite		0.12
kpp_sol	Forward fractional rate of phytate solubilization	min ⁻¹	0.05
kpp_insol	Backward fractional rate of phytate insolubilization	min ⁻¹	
Phytate hydrolysis in the stomach			
Vmax_phytm	Maximum rate of phytate hydrolysis by microbial phytase	g/min/FTU	0.000939
Km_phytm	Affinity constant for phytate hydrolysis by microbial phytase	g	1.74
Vmax_phytp	Maximum rate of phytate hydrolysis by plant phytase	g/min/FTU	0.000234
Km_phytp	Affinity constant for phytate hydrolysis by plant phytase	g	3
Reff_phytm	Relative microbial phytase efficacy in relation to pH		
Reff_phytp	Relative plant phytase efficacy in relation to pH		
kpp_hsi	Fractional rate of phytate hydrolysis in the small intestine	min ⁻¹	0.0045
Phytate insolubilization and complexation in the small intestine			
kpp_insolsi	Fractional rate of phytate insolubilization in the small intestine	min ⁻¹	0.015
ncapp	Stoichiometric number of moles of Ca bound during phytate insolubilization	mol/mol	3
nznpp	Stoichiometric number of moles of Zn bound during phytate insolubilization	mol/mol	0.12
Ca-P complexes formation and insolubilization			
ncap	Stoichiometric number of moles of P bound during Ca-P formation	mol/mol	1.5
Rcanpp	Fractional rate of maximum soluble Ca-NP complex formation	min ⁻¹	0.001
kcanpp	Fractional rate for formation of soluble Ca and soluble NPP complex	min ⁻¹	0.05

Absorption			
Vmaxp	Maximum rate of soluble NPP absorption	g/min	0.00008
Kmp	Affinity constant for soluble NPP absorption	g	0.0004
kap	Fraction rate of soluble NPP absorption	min ⁻¹	0.0001
Vmaxca	Maximum rate of soluble Ca absorption	g/min	0.00014
Kmca	Affinity constant for soluble Ca absorption	g	0.008
kaca	Fraction rate of soluble Ca absorption	min ⁻¹	0.00005
Vmaxzn	Maximum rate of soluble Zn absorption	mg/min	0.0015
kmzn	Affinity constant for soluble Zn absorption	mg	0.008
kazn	Fraction rate of soluble Zn absorption	min ⁻¹	0.00014
Endogenous secretion			
kpos	Positive coefficient that a		0.1
kneg			0.1
rep	Endogenous P secretion in the small intestine	g/L	0.58
reca	Endogenous Ca secretion in the small intestine	g/L	2.0
reznb	Endogenous Zn secretion by bile into in the small intestine	mg/L/dmi	0.90
reznp	Endogenous Zn secretion by the pancreas into in the small intestine	mg/min/dmi	0.06
reznd	Endogenous Zn loss due to cell abrasion in the small intestine	mg/min	0.00002
wp	Molar mass of phosphorus	g/mol	
wca	Molar mass of calcium	g/mol	
wzn	Molar mass of zinc	g/mol	

846 **Table 3**

847 Fluxes of the model, with their corresponding signification and equation.

Flux ¹	Description	Equation ²
Feed intake meal	meal intake	
EXT→SDNPPs SDNPPs→IDNPPs	Intake of non-phytic phosphorus soluble Gastric emptying of non-phytic phosphorus soluble	$meal \times \sum NPP_{diet} \times solnpps_x$ $SDNPPs \times \frac{1}{s_mrtl}$
SDPPs→SDNPPs_m	Hydrolysis of phytic phosphorus by microbial phytase	$\frac{Vmax_phytm \times SDPHYTM \times SDPPs \times Reff_phytm}{Km_phytm + SDPPs}$
SDPPs→SDNPPs_p	Hydrolysis of phytic phosphorus by plant phytase	$\frac{Vmax_phytp \times SDPHYTP \times SDPPs \times Reff_phytp}{Km_phytp + SDPPs}$
EXT→SDNPPi SDNPPi→IDNPPi	Intake of non-phytic phosphorus insoluble Gastric emptying of non-phytic phosphorus insoluble	$meal \times \sum NPP_{diet} \times (1 - solnpps_x)$ $SDNPPi \times \frac{1}{s_mrts}$
EXT→SDPPI SDPPI→IDPPI	Intake of phytic phosphorus Gastric emptying of non-phytic phosphorus insoluble	$meal \times PP_{diet}$ $SDPPI \times \frac{1}{s_mrts}$
SDPPI→SDPPs A_insolpps1	Phytic phosphorus solubilisation Auxiliary equ.1	$kppsol \times SDPPI$ $\frac{Log(\frac{solpp_{inf} - solpp_0}{solpp_0})}{pH_inf}$
kppinsol	Auxiliary equ.2	$\frac{kppsol * A_insolpps1}{(1 - A_insolpps1)}$
SDPPs→SDPPI EXT→SDCaCO3	Phytic phosphorus insolubilisation Intake of calcium from limestone	$kppinsol \times SDPPs$ $meal \times CaCO3_{diet}$

SDCaCO ₃ →IDCas	Gastric emptying of calcium from limestone	$SDCaCO_3 \times \frac{1}{s_mrts}$
SDCaCO ₃ →SDCas EXT→SDCas	Calcium from limestone solubilisation Intake of calcium from mineral and animal sources	$meal \times \sum Ca_{diet}$
SDCas→IDCas	Gastric emptying of calcium soluble	$SDCas \times \frac{1}{s_mrsl}$
EXT→SDCav SDCav→IDCas	Intake of calcium from plant Gastric emptying of plant calcium	$meal \times Cav_{diet}$ $SDCav \times \frac{1}{s_mrts}$
SDCav→SDCas	Solubilisation plant calcium bound to phytic phosphorus	$\min\left(\frac{kppsol \times SDPPi}{wp \times 6} \times ncapp, SDCav\right)$ if pHs < 5 else 0
SDCai→IDCai	Gastric emptying of calcium insoluble	$SDCai \times \frac{1}{s_mrts}$
EXT→SDZns	Intake of zinc from mineral and animal sources	$meal \times \sum Zn_{diet}$
SDZns→IDZns	Gastric emptying of zinc soluble	$SDZns \times \frac{1}{s_mrsl}$
EXT→SDZnv SDZnv→SDZns	Intake of zinc from plant Solubilisation plant zinc bound to phytic phosphorus	$meal \times Znv_{diet}$ $\min\left(\frac{kppsol \times SDPPi}{wp \times 6} \times nznpp, SDZnv\right)$ if pHs < 4 else 0
SDZnv→IDZni	Gastric emptying of vegetal zinc	$SDZnv \times \frac{1}{s_mrts}$
SDZni→IDZni	Gastric emptying of zinc insoluble	$SDZni \times \frac{1}{s_mrts}$
EXT→SDPHYTM SDPHYTM→EXT	Intake of microbial phytase Gastric emptying of microbial phytase	$meal \times PHYTM_{diet}$ $SDPHYTM \times \frac{1}{s_mrsl}$
EXT→SDPHYTV	Intake of vegetal phytase	$meal \times PHYTV_{diet}$

SDPHYTV→ EXT	Gastric emptying of vegetal phytase	$SDPHYTV \times \frac{1}{s_mrtl}$
EXT→ SDQs	Meal intake	$meal \times H_{diet}^+$
SDQs→SDQI	Dissolution of meal in the stomach	$kd \times SDH \times SDQs$
SDQI→ EXT	Gastric emptying of soluble fraction of the meal	$SDQI \times \frac{1}{s_mrtl}$
EXT→SDH	Intake of proton	$meal \times H_{diet}^+$
SDH→ EXT	Gastric emptying of proton	$SDH \times \frac{1}{s_mrtl}$
SDH→Buffer	Buffering effect of meal	$kd \times SDH \times SDQs \times kbbm$
EXTe→SDH	Parietal secretion of proton	$\frac{V0 + (Vsto - V0)}{Vmax}$ $\times \left(Hgs0 + HgsV \times \left(1 - \frac{10^{pHs}}{10^2} \right) \right)$
EXT→SDF	Parietal secretion of fluid	$kgs \times \frac{V0 + (Vsto - V0)}{Vmax}$
EndSec	Auxiliary equ. 3	$Posp = kpos \times (SDQI \rightarrow EXT + SDQs \rightarrow EXT)/dmi$ $NEgp = kneg \times Posp$ $EndSec = (Posp - Negp)$
EXT→IEPs0	Biliary and pancreatic secretion of endogenous phosphorus	$EndSec \times rep \times dmi \times Zn_{diet}$
EXT→IECas0	Biliary and pancreatic secretion of endogenous calcium	$EndSec \times reca \times dmi \times Zn_{diet}$
EXT→IEZns0_b	Biliary secretion of endogenous zinc	$EndSec \times reznb \times dmi \times Zn_{diet}$
EXT→IEZns0_p	Pancreatic secretion of endogenous zinc	$EndSec \times reznp \times dmi \times Zn_{diet}$
EXT→IEZnsd	Desquamation of endogenous zinc	reznd
IDNPPs _j →IDNPPs _{j+1}	Intestinal transit of soluble non phytic phosphorus trough segment j	$IDNPPs_j \times \frac{nseg}{si_mrt}$
IDNPPi _j →IDNPPi _{j+1}	Intestinal transit of insoluble non phytic phosphorus trough segment j	$IDNPPi_j \times \frac{nseg}{si_mrt}$

IDPP _{s_j} →IDPP _{s_{j+1}}	Intestinal transit of soluble phytic phosphorus trough segment j	$IDPP_{s_j} \times \frac{n_{seg}}{si_mrt}$
IDPP _{i_j} →IDPP _{i_{j+1}}	Intestinal transit of insoluble phytic phosphorus trough segment j	$IDPP_{i_j} \times \frac{n_{seg}}{si_mrt}$
IDCas _j →IDCas _{j+1}	Intestinal transit of soluble calcium trough segment j	$IDCas_j \times \frac{n_{seg}}{si_mrt}$
IDCai _j →IDCai _{j+1}	Intestinal transit of insoluble calcium trough segment j	$IDCai_j \times \frac{n_{seg}}{si_mrt}$
IDZns _j →IDZns _{j+1}	Intestinal transit of soluble zinc trough segment j	$IDZns_j \times \frac{n_{seg}}{si_mrt}$
IDZni _j →IDZni _{j+1}	Intestinal transit of insoluble zinc trough segment j	$IDZni_j \times \frac{n_{seg}}{si_mrt}$
IEPs _j →IEPs _{j+1}	Intestinal transit of soluble endogenous phosphorus trough segment j	$IEPs_j \times \frac{n_{seg}}{si_mrt}$
IEP _{i_j} →IEP _{i_{j+1}}	Intestinal transit of insoluble endogenous phosphorus trough segment j	$IEP_{i_j} \times \frac{n_{seg}}{si_mrt}$
IECas _j →IECas _{j+1}	Intestinal transit of soluble endogenous calcium trough segment j	$IECas_j \times \frac{n_{seg}}{si_mrt}$
IECai _j →IECai _{j+1}	Intestinal transit of insoluble endogenous calcium trough segment j	$IECai_j \times \frac{n_{seg}}{si_mrt}$
IEZns _j →IEZns _{j+1}	Intestinal transit of soluble endogenous zinc trough segment j	$IEZns_j \times \frac{n_{seg}}{si_mrt}$
IEZni _j →IEZni _{j+1}	Intestinal transit of insoluble endogenous zinc trough segment j	$IEZni_j \times \frac{n_{seg}}{si_mrt}$
IDNPP _{s_j} →bloodP	Absorption of soluble non phytic phosphorus in the intestine	$\frac{V_{maxp} \times IDNPPs}{K_{mp} + IDNPPs + IEPs} + k_{ap} \times IDNPPs$
IEPs _j →bloodP	Absorption of soluble endogenous phosphorus in the intestine	$\frac{V_{maxp} \times IEPs}{K_{mp} + IDNPPs + IEPs} + k_{ap} \times IEPs$
IDCas _j →bloodCa	Absorption of soluble calcium in the intestine	$\frac{V_{maxca} \times IDCas}{K_{mca} + IDCas + IECas} + k_{aca} \times IDCas$
IECas _j →bloodCa	Absorption of soluble endogenous calcium in the intestine	$\frac{V_{maxca} \times IECas}{K_{mca} + IDCas + IECas} + k_{aca} \times IECas$

IDZns _j →bloodZn	Absorption of soluble zinc in the intestine	$\frac{V_{maxzn} \times IDZns}{K_{mzn} + IDZns + IEZns} + k_{azn} \times IDZns$
IEZns _j →bloodZn	Absorption of soluble endogenous zinc in the intestine	$\frac{V_{maxzn} \times IEZns}{K_{mzn} + IDZns + IEZns} + k_{azn} \times IEZns$
IDPPs _j →IDPPi _j	Phytic phosphorus insolubilisation in the intestine	$k_{ppinsolsi} \times IDPPs$
IDPPs _j →IDNPPs _j	Phytic phosphorus hydrolysis in the intestine	$k_{pp_hsi} \times IDPPs$
IDCas _j →IDCai _j	Insolubilisation of dietary calcium by phytic phosphorus	$\min\left(\frac{k_{pphis} \times IDPPs}{wp \times 6} \times ncapp \times wca, IDCas\right)$
IECas _j →IECas _j	Insolubilisation of endogenous calcium by phytic phosphorus	$\min\left(\frac{k_{pphis} \times IDPPs}{wp \times 6} \times ncapp \times wca, IECas\right)$
IDZns _j →IDZni _j	Insolubilisation of dietary zinc by phytic phosphorus	$\min\left(\frac{k_{pphis} \times IDPPs}{wp \times 6} \times nznpp \times wca, IDZns\right)$
IEZns _j →IEZns _j	Insolubilisation of endogenous zinc by phytic phosphorus	$\min\left(\frac{k_{pphis} \times IDPPs}{wp \times 6} \times nznpp \times wca, IEZns\right)$
Rnppca	Auxiliary equ.4	$1 \text{ if } > \frac{(IDNPPs_j + IEPs_j) \times wp}{(IDCas_j + IECas_j) \times wca} \text{ else } 0$
IDCas _j →IDCai _{j_cap}	Insolubilisation of dietary calcium by formation of complexes between soluble calcium and soluble non phytic phosphorus	$k_{canpp} \times IDCas_j$
IDNPPs _j →IDNPPi _{j_cap}	Insolubilisation of dietary non phytic phosphorus by formation of complexes between soluble calcium and soluble non phytic phosphorus	$\frac{k_{canpp} \times IDCas_j}{wca} \times ncap \times wp$

848 ¹ Pool names : the first letter stands for the location (S =Stomach; and I = Intestinal), the second for the origin (D = Dietary; and E =
849 Endogenous), the third for the species (Ca = Calcium, NPP = Non-Phytic Phosphorus, PP = Phytic Phosphorus, and P =
850 Phosphorus) and the fourth for the form (s = soluble and i = insoluble)

851 ² Model parameters are defined in Table 2

852

853 **Table 4**

854 Apparent digestibility and digestible content of diets containing different calcium and
 855 phytase levels after a simulation of 1440min. LCa = low calcium; CCa = control
 856 calcium; PhytM = microbial phytase (0, 500, or 2000 FTU/kg).

	LCa		CCa		
	PhytM0	PhytM500	PhytM0	PhytM500	PhytM2000
AID, %					
PP	22.5	81.1	22.5	80.7	88.8
P	55.3	76.3	50.2	69.2	73.5
Ca	64.4	69.6	61.7	67.2	68.0
Zn	50.0	77.8	47.3	77.0	81.6
Digestible, g/kg					
PP	0.6	2.1	0.6	2.1	2.3
P	3.4	3.4	3.1	3.0	3.2
Ca	3.4	2.6	5.3	4.7	4.8
Zn	45.0	70.0	42.6	69.3	73.4

857

858

859 **Table 5**

860 Sensitivity of output parameters of the digestion model¹

Model parameters	Set	Change	CCa-PhytM500			
			AID PP, %	ATTD Ca, %	ATTD P, %	ATTD Zn, %
References			80.70	67.20	69.20	77.00
Passage						
si_mrt	180	90	0.04	0.45	-0.10	-0.14
si_mrt	180	135	0.02	0.33	-0.10	-0.12
si_mrt	180	225	0.00	0.21	-0.10	-0.08
si_mrt	180	270	0.01	0.17	-0.09	-0.06
s_mrtl	95	48	0.50	0.32	0.39	0.55
s_mrtl	95	71	0.42	0.25	0.32	0.49
s_mrtl	95	118	0.29	0.16	0.22	0.36
s_mrtl	95	1143	0.25	0.13	0.19	0.32
s_mrts	163	82	0.06	0.00	0.04	0.18
s_mrts	163	122	0.03	0.00	0.02	0.13
s_mrts	163	204	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.09
s_mrts	163	245	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.08
Gastric secretion						
Vs0	0.162	0.081	0.16	0.11	0.08	0.18
Vs0	0.162	0.1215	0.03	0.00	0.01	0.03
Vs0	0.162	0.2025	-0.01	0.00	-0.01	-0.01
Vs0	0.162	0.243	-0.02	-0.01	-0.02	-0.02
Vsmax	2	1	0.09	0.02	0.05	0.09
Vsmax	2	1.5	0.06	0.02	0.04	0.06
Vsmax	2	2.5	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01
Vsmax	2	3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
kgs	0.01	0.005	-0.03	-0.01	-0.02	-0.04
kgs	0.01	0.0075	-0.04	-0.01	-0.02	-0.04
kgs	0.01	0.0125	-0.04	-0.02	-0.03	-0.05
kgs	0.01	0.015	-0.05	-0.02	-0.03	-0.05
Hgs0	20	10	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01
Hgs0	20	15	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01
Hgs0	20	25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Hgs0	20	30	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Hgsv	60	30	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.04
Hgsv	60	45	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.03
Hgsv	60	75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Hgsv	60	90	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
kd	0.2	0.1	0.00	-0.01	0.00	0.00
kd	0.2	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

kd	0.2	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
kd	0.2	0.3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Phytate solubilisation						
solpp_0	0.88	0.44	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
solpp_0	0.88	0.66	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
solpp_0	0.88	1.10	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01
solpp_0	0.88	1.32	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
solpp_inf	0.12	0.06	-0.11	-0.03	-0.07	-0.14
solpp_inf	0.12	0.09	-0.13	-0.04	-0.08	-0.15
solpp_inf	0.12	0.15	-0.19	-0.06	-0.12	-0.22
solpp_inf	0.12	10.18	-0.21	-0.06	-0.13	-0.22
kpp_sol	0.05	0.03	0.08	0.03	0.05	0.09
kpp_sol	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.02	0.03	0.06
kpp_sol	0.05	0.06	0.03	0.00	0.01	0.03
kpp_sol	0.05	0.08	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03
Phytate hydrolysis						
vmax_phytm	0.0009	0.0005	0.43	0.10	0.28	0.43
vmax_phytm	0.0009	0.0007	0.36	0.09	0.23	0.38
vmax_phytm	0.0009	0.0012	0.25	0.05	0.15	0.29
vmax_phytm	0.0009	0.0014	0.22	0.05	0.14	0.26
km_phytm	1.738	0.869	-0.32	-0.07	-0.20	-0.39
km_phytm	1.738	1.3035	-0.29	-0.07	-0.18	-0.34
km_phytm	1.738	2.1725	-0.25	-0.06	-0.16	-0.27
km_phytm	1.738	2.607	-0.23	-0.06	-0.15	-0.24
kpp_hsi	0.0045	0.0023	0.10	0.01	0.05	0.07
kpp_hsi	0.0045	0.0034	0.09	0.01	0.05	0.07
kpp_hsi	0.0045	0.0056	0.09	0.01	0.05	0.07
kpp_hsi	0.0045	0.0068	0.08	0.01	0.05	0.07
Phytate insolubilization and complexation in the small intestine						
kpp_insolsi	0.0150	0.0075	-0.11	-0.05	-0.04	-0.29
kpp_insolsi	0.0150	0.0113	-0.09	-0.03	-0.03	-0.24
kpp_insolsi	0.0150	0.0188	-0.06	-0.03	-0.02	-0.17
kpp_insolsi	0.0150	0.0225	-0.06	-0.02	-0.02	-0.15
nznpp	0.1200	0.0600	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.48
nznpp	0.1200	0.0900	0.00	0.01	0.00	-0.45
nznpp	0.1200	0.1500	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.40
nznpp	0.1200	0.1800	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.38
ncapp	3.0000	1.5	0.00	-0.08	0.01	0.00
ncapp	3.0000	2.25	0.00	-0.07	0.01	0.00
ncapp	3.0000	3.75	0.00	-0.07	0.00	0.00
ncapp	3.0000	4.5	0.00	-0.07	0.01	0.00
Ca-P complexes formation and insolubilization						
Rcanpp	0.0011	0.0006	0.00	-0.06	-0.17	0.00

Rcanpp	0.0011	0.0008	0.00	-0.06	-0.16	0.01
Rcanpp	0.0011	0.0014	0.00	-0.07	-0.16	-0.01
Rcanpp	0.0011	0.0017	0.00	-0.06	-0.14	0.00
kcanpp	0.0500	0.0250	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
kcanpp	0.0500	0.0375	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
kcanpp	0.0500	0.0625	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
kcanpp	0.0500	0.0750	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Absorption						
vmaxp	0.0001	0.0001	0.00	0.00	0.13	0.00
vmaxp	0.0001	0.0001	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.00
vmaxp	0.0001	0.0001	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.00
vmaxp	0.0001	0.0002	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.00
kmp	0.0004	0.0002	0.00	0.00	-0.03	0.00
kmp	0.0004	0.0003	-0.01	0.00	-0.03	-0.01
kmp	0.0004	0.0005	0.00	0.00	-0.02	0.00
kmp	0.0004	0.0006	0.00	0.00	-0.02	0.00
kap	0.0001	0.0001	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
kap	0.0001	0.0001	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
kap	0.0001	0.0001	-0.01	0.00	0.00	-0.01
kap	0.0001	0.0002	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
vmaxca	0.0001	0.0001	0.00	0.87	0.04	0.00
vmaxca	0.0001	0.0001	0.00	0.73	0.04	0.00
vmaxca	0.0001	0.0002	-0.01	0.50	0.04	-0.01
vmaxca	0.0001	0.0002	0.00	0.41	0.04	0.00
kmca	0.0080	0.0040	0.00	-0.34	-0.02	0.00
kmca	0.0080	0.0060	0.00	-0.32	-0.01	0.01
kmca	0.0080	0.0100	0.00	-0.30	-0.01	0.00
kmca	0.0080	0.0120	0.00	-0.28	-0.01	0.00
kaca	0.0001	0.0000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
kaca	0.0001	0.0000	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
kaca	0.0001	0.0001	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
kaca	0.0001	0.0001	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
vmaxzn	0.0015	0.0007	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.28
vmaxzn	0.0015	0.0011	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.15
vmaxzn	0.0015	0.0018	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14
vmaxzn	0.0015	0.0022	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.13
kmzn	0.0008	0.0004	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.04
kmzn	0.0008	0.0006	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.03
kmzn	0.0008	0.0010	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.02
kmzn	0.0008	0.0012	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.03
kazn	0.0001	0.0001	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
kazn	0.0001	0.0001	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
kazn	0.0001	0.0002	0.00	-0.01	0.00	0.00

kazn	0.0001	0.0002	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
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861 ¹ Sensitivity was calculated as described by Schop et al. (2023). A positive sensitivity indicates an
862 increase in the output with increasing input, whereas a negative value indicates a decrease. The
863 absolute sensitivity value (|S|) ranges from 0 (no response) to 1 (proportional response), with higher
864 values indicating greater sensitivity.

865 **Table 6**

866 Evaluation of the model, presenting goodness of fit of observed (obs) vs predicted (pred) apparent digestibility (%) in growing pigs.

Nutrient	n_{exp}	n_{obs}	Obs (SD)	Pred (SD)	R^2	RMPSE (%)	ECT (%)	ER (%)	ED (%)	intercept	slope	Cb	ν	μ	CCC
Ca	36	156	61.6 (13.38)	58.1 (13.49)	0.48	12.4	21.2	5.7	73.1	3.80	0.88	0.97	0.99	0.26	0.84
P	55	230	52.0 (17.13)	49.8 (16.54)	0.91	8.9	24.5	0.1	75.4	-0.26	0.94	0.99	1.03	0.12	0.96
PP	5	29	57.9 (34.21)	62.7 (32.51)	0.97	11.7	47.7	1.4	50.9	7.22	0.96	0.99	1.04	-0.14	0.98
Zn	18	119	27.7 (12.93)	41.0 (11.58)	0.43	76.9	39.2	24.5	36.3	39.11	0.07	0.63	1.12	- 1.090	0.05

867 Abbreviations: Ca = Calcium; P = Phosphorus; PP = Phytic Phosphorus; Zn = Zinc; RMSPE = root mean square prediction error (as % of observed mean),
868 ECT = error of overall bias, ER = error due to deviation of the regression slope from unity, ED = error due to disturbance (i.e. random error), where ECT, ER,
869 and ED are expressed as % of mean square prediction error. CCC = Lin's concordance correlation coefficient, Cb = Bias correction factor, ν = measure of
870 scale shift and μ = measure of location shift

871 **Figure captions**

872

873

874 **Fig. 1.** Forester diagram of the model the digestive fluxes of calcium, phosphorus
875 and zinc in growing pigs. SI = Small Intestine; S = Stomach; I = Intestine; PP = Phytic
876 Phosphorus; NPP = Non Phytic Phosphorus; Ca = Calcium; Zn = Zinc; s = soluble
877 and i = insoluble.

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881 **Fig. 2.** Cumulative pools from the in and out fluxes of H⁺ pool (bar) and absolute H⁺
 882 (line) in the stomach compartment from CCa-PhytM0 (Ca : 7.8g/kg) and LCa-PhytM0
 883 (Ca = 4.4 g/kg) diets.

884

885

886 **Fig. 3.** pH of the gastric contents after an ingestion of 300g of CCa-PhytM0 (Ca:

887 7.8g/kg, BC: meq/kg) and LCa-PhytM0 (Ca = 4.4 g/kg, BC: meq/kg) diets.

888

889

890 **Fig. 4.** Simulated dynamics of soluble (A) and insoluble (B) phytate phosphorus
 891 (SDPPs, SDPPi), soluble non-phytate phosphorus (C; SDNPPs), and phytate
 892 hydrolysis (D) rate under different calcium and phytase levels. LCa = low calcium;
 893 CCa = control calcium; PhytM = microbial phytase (0, 500, or 2000 FTU/kg).

894

895

896 **Fig. 5.** Simulated disappearance kinetics of soluble phytate phosphorus (IDPPs; A),
 897 soluble non-phytate phosphorus (IDNPPs; B), calcium (IDCa; C), and zinc (IDZn; D)
 898 along the intestinal segments, expressed as percentage of intake, under different
 899 calcium and phytase levels. LCa = low calcium; CCa = control calcium; PhytM =
 900 microbial phytase (0, 500, or 2000 FTU/kg).

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902

903 **Fig. 6.** Simulated flux of absorption of soluble non-phytic phosphorus (NPPs, A);
 904 soluble dietary zinc (IDZns; B), soluble dietary calcium (IDCas; C) and soluble
 905 endogenous calcium (IECas; D) under different calcium and phytase levels. LCa =
 906 low calcium; CCa = control calcium; PhytM = microbial phytase (0, 500, or 2000
 907 FTU/kg).

908

909

910 **Fig. 7.** Comparing observed and predicted values of phytic phosphorus (A), phosphorus (B); calcium (C) and zinc (D) of apparent
 911 ileal (AID) or total tract (ATTD) digestibility. Data are adjusted for experiment effect. Regression line (—) and Y = X line (- -).

